

Link Kuesioner:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeuO-AVXoeLy5Zh6CLOK_I9mK1pilZcSsjcR16x3qG-EI4Rvw/viewform?usp=sharing&oid=111690783645491152523

Link Jawaban Responden dari Kuesioner (Spreadsheet)

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1yoDZ6bKajHN6tSj3zUOmSmK6NgUjhzaAOY5xVST0DrM/edit?usp=sharing>